
**Impact of Nitrogen fertilizers on the sustainability of *Alternaria porri* (Ellis)
in the field of onion.**

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Abstract:

Alternaria porri is the most common pathogen associated with the leaf of onion causing the disease purple blotch (Dongre, M.A and Borse, K.N. 2015). It affects the green mature leaves of onion (Suheri and Price, 2001). The spores which are present in the soil as well as in the air get germinate on leaves and produce minute water-soaked spots, which later turn to brown and dark brown. Onion crops require high nitrogenous fertilizers (Gebretsadik, K., Dechassa, N. 2018). At least 1 to 1.5 kg of Nitrogenous fertilizer per 100 feet row of onion crop. The ammonium sulfate or ammonium nitrate are the main fertilizers use to compensate the N₂ level for the onion crop (Andreas *et al.* 2003). This leads to reducing the pH of the soil and increases the acidity of the soil (www.blinc.com/role-nitrogen-fertilizer-soil-ph).

Keywords: *Alternaria*, Blotch, Fertilizer, etc.

Introduction:

In Maharashtra 3 seasons are well remarked with weather conditions hot, rainy, or cold. On this basis summer, rainy season, and Winter are the main seasons (Maharashtra tourism). Farmers also grown crops that are suitable in their respective seasons. Some crops are affected by season while others are affected very less or unaffected by seasonal changes. One of such crops is the Onion crop, grown throughout the year in some parts of Maharashtra like North Maharashtra specifically the Khandesh region. Crop grown in three seasons in this area requires at least 7 to 8 months for seed sowing to harvesting. Early Kharif (February to September), Kharif (May to December), and Rabi (October to May) (Vinod Kumar 2012)

The pathogen *Alternaria porri* remain as mycelium in onion leaf debris of diseased plant, the older leaves are more susceptible to this (Ambayeba, 2018).

Material and Method:

Identification and isolation of pathogen *A. porri* (Ellis) (Barnett and Hunter 1998 and Sehu Aliero 2010)

Diseased plants were collected from the field of onion in a sterilized plastic bag. In the laboratory, the diseased portion was inoculated on a PDA medium supplemented with ampicillin to check bacterial growth. The inoculated plate was later placed in the dark at 28- 30°C for a week. Later culture was placed on a glass slide with cotton blue, staining, and morphology to confirm the pathogen.

Disease symptoms

Spores which are present in the soil as well as in air get germinate on leaves and produce minute water-soaked spots, which later turn to brown and dark brown. The spots are rarely round but mostly oval, fully grown diseased with loaded spore, the spot looks purple or dark purple with a yellow margin.

Plate 1: Section of leaf of onion showing *Alternaria* conidia and hyphae and Conidia of *A. porri*.

2. Culture character and morphology of pathogen

Initially on PDA media colony seems white which later converted to dark coloured. The mature colony is blackish in colour on the ventral side slightly yellowish in colour. Conidiophores are brownish which may arise solitary or in groups, generally cylindrical and septate. Conidia ranges from 89 to 295 μm in length while the thickness varied from 12 to 18 μm . each conidia show distinct beak, transverse and longitudinal septation is prominent. Transverse septa may be 5 to 10 and longitudinal septa are 2 to 4 in number.

Selection of plot

In field some area of onion crop is purposefully kept untreated with N_2 fertilizer throughout the growing season i.e., from transplanting to harvesting. While remaining field were supplied with N_2 fertilizers. Other chemicals including phosphate, potash and pesticides were applied to both control plot and N_2 treated plot in same ways.

Plate 2 : Pure culture of *A. porri* isolated from

diseased onion leaf.

Collection of diseased plant from field

Analyzing untreated or control plot and counted the numbers of plants on which leaves shows distinct disease symptoms of purple blotch. Same are of N_2 fertilizer treated plot were also analyzed for same purple blotch disease. Data for successive three years were analyzed and use to calculate chances of occurrence of disease in control and N_2 fertilizer treated plot.

Same process of counting and analyzing of plant were repeated in interval of month and tried to analyze any difference. The data were collected after transplanting and before harvesting time September, October and November.

Plate 3. Collection sites Observations

1. Observation table

Observation number	N2 free crop / Crop treated with N2 fertilizer	No. of plants analyzed			Number of plants shows symptoms of disease			Chances of occurrence of disease (%)
		September	October	November	September	October	November	
1st year								
1.	Control	200	200	200	3	14	17	5.667%
2.	Treated with N2 fertilizer	200	200	200	6	11	21	6.333%
2nd year								
3.	Control	200	200	200	09	13	17	6.5%
4.	Treated with N2 fertilizer	200	200	200	7	11	16	5.667%
3rd year								
5.	Control	200	200	200	04	09	11	4%
6.	Treated with N2 fertilizer	200	200	200	08	10	12	5%

Table1: Three-year data of incidence of disease in respective three month for successive three years

Result

In three successive year it was observed that N₂ fertilizer is not significantly affecting the growth of *Alternaria porri*. The chances of occurrence of disease in N₂ free plot is ranges from 4% to 6.5 % while in plot where N₂ fertilizer were supplied it ranges between 5% to 6.333 %.

Graph: - Chances of occurrence of *Alternaria porri* causing purple blotch disease on leaves of onion in N₂ free crop and crop treated with N₂ fertilizer

Discussion

Alternaria porri (Ellis) causing purple blotch on onion leaves. The field in which N₂ fertilizer is not supplied, the onion crop is stunted in height and bulb size is also small. In spite of that incident of occurrence of purple blotch disease seems to be unaffected. There is no any direct impact of nitrogenous fertilizer supply and disease development and growth of pathogen.

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